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Undergraduate Research Internship:

Neutrino Oscillations and Quantum Informa- tion Theory

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that an internship project entitled ”**Neutrino Oscillations and Quantum Information Theory**” submitted by **Mr. Baktiar Wasir Farooq**, a student of B.Sc. (Hons.) Physics **ROLL NO.23036567022**, Department of Physics, Kirori Mal College, University of Delhi, is a record of original work carried out by him under our supervision under the Skill Enhancement Course (S.E.C) Internship Program (I.A.C).

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We further certify that this work has not been submitted to any other institution or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

We recommend that this internship report be accepted in fulfillment of the requirements (official) for the degree of Bachelor of Science (Honors) in physics.

Neutrino Oscillations and Quantum Information Theory

Baktiar Wasir Farooq

Abstract

Neutrino oscillation is a quantum mechanical phenomenon wherein neutrinos change their flavor as they propagate through space, arising from the mixing between flavor and mass eigenstates described by the Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata (PMNS) matrix. This discovery established that neutrinos possess nonzero masses and provided evidence for physics beyond the Standard Model.

The project extends the analysis to the **Quantum Information Theory (QIT)** framework by quantifying flavor entanglement and coherence among neutrino states. Using measures such as von Neumann entropy and relative entropy of coherence, the study demonstrates how neutrino mixing generates dynamic quantum correlations among flavor modes. These correlations satisfy the Complete Complementarity Relation, highlighting a trade-off between predictability, coherence, and entanglement.

Furthermore, in this study, a computational investigation of three-flavor neutrino oscillations is performed using Python, incorporating experimentally determined mixing angles, mass-squared differences, and the CP-violating phase. The oscillation probabilities for various transitions — $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\mu$, $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\tau$, and $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$ — are analyzed as functions of the ratio L/E for different CP phases ($\delta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ, 180^\circ$). The results reveal that the CP phase significantly affects both the amplitude and phase of oscillations, leading to measurable asymmetries between neutrino and antineutrino behavior.

Overall, this combined quantum–computational approach bridges neutrino oscillation physics with quantum information theory, offering new insight into the role of quantum correlations in particle flavor evolution and the fundamental nature of CP violation.

Declaration

I certify that

1. The work contained in this undergraduate dissertation is original and has been completed by me under the guidance of my supervisors.
2. The work has not been submitted to any other institute for any degree or diploma.
3. Whenever I have used materials (data, graphs, theoretical analysis, and text) from other sources, I have given due credit to the original source and author by citing them in the text of the thesis and listing the details in the bibliography.
4. Whenever I have quoted written materials from other sources, I have given due credit to the sources.

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Introduction:

Neutrinos are among the most intriguing and least understood particles in the Standard Model of particle physics. They are electrically neutral, possess extremely small masses, and interact only via weak interactions, making their detection and characterization a challenging endeavor.

The discovery of *neutrino oscillations* provided the first clear evidence that neutrinos have mass and that lepton flavor is not conserved in weak interactions. This phenomenon implies that the flavor eigenstates (ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ) are superpositions of the mass eigenstates (ν_1, ν_2, ν_3), connected through the PMNS (Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata) mixing matrix.

0.0.1 Neutrino Oscillation Phenomenon

Neutrino oscillation arises when a neutrino produced in a specific flavor state propagates through space and is detected as a different flavor state. The probability of this flavor transition depends on:

- The differences between the squared masses of the neutrino mass eigenstates (Δm_{ij}^2),
- The mixing angles ($\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23}$),
- The ratio of the propagation distance L to the neutrino energy E ,
- The CP-violating phase δ_{CP} .

0.0.2 Significance of the Study

Understanding the oscillation behavior and the role of the CP-violating phase is vital in modern neutrino physics. Determining the value of δ_{CP} can provide insights into the matter–antimatter asymmetry of the Universe. This research employs a computational approach to analyze three-flavor neutrino oscillations by numerically evaluating transition probabilities for various CP phases using Python.

0.0.3 Objectives

The main objectives of this research are:

1. To model neutrino oscillations using the three-flavor mixing formalism.
2. To compute survival and transition probabilities for different CP-violating phases.
3. To analyze the effect of δ_{CP} on oscillation amplitudes and phases.
4. To visualize the oscillation patterns and quantify flavor entanglement using entropy measures.

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Chapter 1

Neutrino Oscillations

1.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I would try to cover the basics of Neutrino oscillations starting from 2 flavors to 3 flavors. Initially I will cover the history behind the Ideas of Neutrinos, then go forward to talk about the properties of neutrinos and it's general formalisms. This would give an idea of what exactly neutrinos are and how do they change flavor over time.

1.2 History of Neutrinos

We all must know about the *beta decay* ($\beta - decay$). It is a weak interaction process in which a nucleon (neutron or proton) changes into another by exchanging a W^\pm boson. There are 2 types of beta-decay:

- 1) Positive $\beta - decay$
- 2) Negative $\beta - decay$

1.2.1 Negative Beta Decay

Here, a neutron gets converted to a proton, with an emission of electron (e^-). The interacting particle here is the W^- vector boson.

Generalized one:

This equation gives us the idea of negative beta decay. Here, basically a Boron with 5 protons gets converted to Carbon with 6 protons with emission of an electron.

1.2.2 Positive Beta Decay

Here, a proton gets converted to a neutron, with an emission of positron (e^+). The interacting particle here is the W^+ vector boson.

Generalized one:

This equation gives us the idea of positive beta decay. Here, basically an Oxygen atom with 8 protons gets converted to a Nitrogen atom with 7 neutrons with emission of a positron.

1.2.3 Issue with the Energy Distribution Graph

Solving the 2 body decay problem of the unstable nuclei, we get :

Representing the Momentum 4-vector:

$$P_A^u = \left(\frac{E_A}{c}, 0, 0, 0 \right)$$

$$P_B^u = \left(\frac{E_B}{c}, P_B^1, P_B^2, P_B^3 \right)$$

$$P_e^u = \left(\frac{E_e}{c}, P_e^1, P_e^2, P_e^3 \right)$$

By the law of conservation of momentum:

$$P_A^u = P_B^u + P_e^u$$

Hence,

$$P_e^u = P_A^u - P_B^u$$

Taking the inner product (squaring both sides), we get:

$$\|P_e^u\|^2 = \|P_A^u - P_B^u\|^2$$

Using the Lorentz Transformation matrix:

$$\|P_A^u\| = \begin{bmatrix} E_A/c \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E_A/c & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This results to: $\|P_e^u\|^2 = -(E_A/c)^2 = -m_A^2 c^2$

Also,

$$P_A^u P_B^u = \begin{bmatrix} E_A/c \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E_B/c & P_B^1 & P_B^2 & P_B^3 \end{bmatrix}$$

This results to: $-E_A E_B / c^2$ So, finally we use these relations in the above equation and we get the energy of e^- :

$$E_e = \left(\frac{m_A^2 c^2 + m_B^2 c^2 + m_e^2 c^2}{2m_A} \right) \quad (1.1)$$

The energy of electron is a constant. On basis of this theoretical calculation and observational results, the Relative probability of electrons vs Energy is:

Figure 1.1: This graph is the plot between Energy vs Probability of electrons. The blue plot is the observational result and the red line is the theoretical plot.

Source: <https://t2k-experiment.org/neutrinos/a-brief-history/betaspec>

Now, the main question and the mystery was why exactly did the observational and experimental results show such unexpected results?

So, clearly from the graph, some energy is missing and hence this problem was named the "Missing Energy Problem".

Later in 1930, an Austrian-Swiss physicist Wolfgang Pauli, he said that there might be some particle that also release during the Beta decay reaction which takes the rest of the energy and is known as neutrino and anti-neutrino depending on the type of decay. The symbol of neutrino is a Greek letter (nu): ν So, the equation of β -decay now turns out

to be \rightarrow

Positive Beta Decay:

Generalized one:

Negative Beta Decay:

Generalized one:

1.3 Two-Flavor Neutrino Oscillation

1.3.1 Solar Neutrino Problem (for Vacuum)

Till now we came to know how the 1st generation of neutrinos (i.e. the ν_e).

At the core of the sun, various beta decay reactions take place due to which ν_e are produced. **Raymond Davis**, a researcher in the **Brookhaven National Laboratory** carried out an experiment to determine the neutrinos during the solar reactions. He basically carried out **Homestake experiment** to get the electron neutrino flux. But there were shocking results! Only 1/3rd of the theoretical data was observed from the experimental observations. This was the **The Solar Neutrino Problem!**

Figure 1.2: the plot of the observation of Raymond Davis for a year of (1964-1980)

1 solar neutrino unit (or 1 SNU) = 1 neutrino is being captured in 10^{36} second

Later, it was found that a part of ν_e got converted to ν_μ . This was the beginning era of Neutrino Oscillations.

1.3.2 Two- Flavor Neutrino Oscillation Formalism

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta \\ -\sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, the ν_1 and ν_2 are mass eigen states with masses m_1 and m_2 , respectively, such that $\Delta m \neq 0$ and $\theta \neq 0$.

$$\hat{H} |\psi_i\rangle = E_i |\psi_i\rangle$$

This gives us:

$$|\psi_i(t)\rangle = |\psi_i(t=0)\rangle e^{\frac{iE_i t}{\hbar}}$$

Now, for the Neutrino at time $t=0$,

$$|\nu_e(t=0)\rangle = \cos\theta |\nu_1(0)\rangle + \sin\theta |\nu_2(0)\rangle$$

Similarly, for time t ,

$$|\nu_e(t)\rangle = \cos\theta e^{\frac{iE_1 t}{\hbar}} |\nu_1(0)\rangle + \sin\theta e^{\frac{iE_2 t}{\hbar}} |\nu_2(0)\rangle$$

Now, by representing $|\nu_1\rangle$ and $|\nu_2\rangle$ in terms of the flavor states:

$$|\nu_e(t)\rangle = \cos\theta e^{\frac{iE_1 t}{\hbar}} (\cos\theta |\nu_e\rangle - \sin\theta |\nu_\mu\rangle) + \sin\theta e^{\frac{iE_2 t}{\hbar}} (\cos\theta |\nu_e\rangle + \sin\theta |\nu_\mu\rangle)$$

On further simplifying we get,

$$|\nu_e(t)\rangle = (\cos^2\theta e^{-iE_1 t} + \sin^2\theta e^{-iE_2 t}) |\nu_e\rangle + (\sin\theta \cos\theta e^{iE_2 t} - \cos\theta \sin\theta e^{iE_1 t}) |\nu_\mu\rangle$$

Now if I want to find the survival probability:

$$P_{(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e, t)} = |\langle \nu_e | \nu(t) \rangle|^2$$

We finally get:

$$P_{(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e, t)} = 1 - \sin^2 2\theta \sin^2 \left(\frac{(E_2 - E_1)t}{2} \right) \quad (1.2)$$

To get the Oscillation Probability:

$$P_{(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\mu, t)} = 1 - P_{(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e, t)} \quad (1.3)$$

Now, we need to focus on the phase term of the 2 flavor Neutrino Oscillation.

$$E_i = \sqrt{P_i^2 + m_i^2}$$

By using the Binomial Expansion:

$$E_i = P_i + \frac{m_i^2}{2P_i}. \text{ Here, } i=1,2.$$

Using the Equal Momentum Approximation:

$$E_2 - E_1 = \frac{m_2^2 - m_1^2}{2P} \approx \frac{m_2^2 - m_1^2}{2E}$$

Getting back to the phase term: $\frac{E_2 - E_1 t}{2} = \frac{\Delta m^2 (eV^2)}{4E (eV)} L(m)$ So, we can see dimensionally that the phase term has unit eV-m! as we know that the Phase is dimensionless and since, $\hbar c = 1.97 \times 10^{-7} eVm$. So, we divide the phase term by $\hbar c$. Which results to: $1.27 \frac{\Delta m^2 (eV^2)}{E (MeV)} L(m)$
 Finally we get the expression for the Survival Probability of Neutrino!
 Which is:

$$P_{(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e, t)} = 1 - \sin^2 2\theta \sin^2 \left(1.27 \frac{\Delta m^2 (eV^2) L(m)}{E (MeV)} \right) \quad (1.4)$$

Here, L is the baseline length in meters.

E is the average energy of the neutrino flux detected by the detector in MeV.

θ is the mixing angle.

1.4 Three-Flavor Neutrino Oscillation

1.4.1 P.M.N.S Matrix Basic Idea

The Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata or PMNS matrix describes the mixing between the neutrino flavor eigenstates (ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ) and the mass eigenstates (ν_1, ν_2, ν_3) having masses (m_1, m_2, m_3), respectively:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} = U_{\text{PMNS}} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \nu_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

1.4.2 SU(2) Rotation: Two-Flavor Mixing

For two neutrino flavors, the mixing matrix belongs to the group

$$SU(2),$$

the group of 2×2 unitary matrices with a determinant of 1.

The general $SU(2)$ mixing matrix can be written as:

$$U_{SU(2)} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta e^{-i\phi} \\ -\sin \theta e^{i\phi} & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1.5)$$

where ϕ is a complex phase.

Absence of CP Violation in $SU(2)$

The interesting fact is that this phase ϕ is not physical as it can be deleted by rephrasing the neutrino fields:

$$\nu_1 \rightarrow e^{i\alpha} \nu_1, \quad \nu_2 \rightarrow e^{i\beta} \nu_2. \quad (1.6)$$

After this transformation, the mixing matrix becomes real. Therefore,

The mixing matrix cannot have any phase and hence, can not exhibit CP violation.
--

(1.7)

1.4.3 $SU(3)$ Rotation: Three-Flavor Mixing

For three neutrino flavors, the mixing matrix belongs to the group

$$SU(3),$$

the group of 3×3 unitary matrices with unit determinant.

A general 3×3 unitary matrix contains three mixing angles and six phases.

Five of these phases can be omitted by field redefinitions, leaving

3 mixing angles + 1 physical CP-violating phase.
--

(1.8)

This remaining phase is the Dirac CP phase δ .

1.4.4 PMNS Matrix as an $SU(3)$ Rotation

The PMNS matrix is written as

$$U_{\text{PMNS}} = R_{23} R_{13}(\delta) R_{12}, \quad (1.9)$$

where

$$R_{12} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1.10)$$

$$R_{23} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1.11)$$

$$R_{13}(\delta) = \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{i\delta} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.12)$$

Here $c_{ij} = \cos \theta_{ij}$ and $s_{ij} = \sin \theta_{ij}$.

1.4.5 Reactor Neutrino Case

In reactor neutrino experiments, the oscillation effectively probes only the 1–3 sector of the PMNS matrix. The effective mixing matrix reduces to

$$U_{\text{reactor}} \approx R_{13}(\delta). \quad (1.13)$$

Although the CP phase δ appears in this matrix, the observable quantity is the survival probability

$$P(\bar{\nu}_e \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e), \quad (1.14)$$

which depends only on

$$|U_{e1}|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad |U_{e3}|^2. \quad (1.15)$$

Since

$$|U_{e3}|^2 = \sin^2 \theta_{13}, \quad (1.16)$$

the CP phase cancels out.

1.4.6 Physical Interpretation

- SU(2) mixing has no physical CP phase due to absorption of phase.
- SU(3) mixing necessarily contains one physical CP phase.
- Reactor oscillations are effectively two-flavor but originate from an SU(3) theory.
- CP violation becomes observable only in three-flavor appearance oscillations.

Conclusion: CP violation in neutrino oscillations requires at least three flavors.

(1.17)

The standard parameterization of the PMNS matrix is:

$$U_{\text{PMNS}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{i\delta} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Multiplying these matrices gives:

$$U_{\text{PMNS}} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{23}c_{13} \end{pmatrix}$$

where $s_{ij} = \sin \theta_{ij}$ and $c_{ij} = \cos \theta_{ij}$.

If Majorana phases are included, an additional diagonal phase matrix $\text{diag}(1, e^{i\alpha_1/2}, e^{i\alpha_2/2})$ is multiplied on the right.

$$U_{\text{PMNS}}^{(\text{Majorana})} = U_{\text{PMNS}} \cdot \text{diag}(1, e^{i\alpha_1/2}, e^{i\alpha_2/2})$$

But as of now I will be constrained with the Dirac Neutrinos rather than

Majorana Neutrinos.

1.4.7 Three-Flavor Neutrino Oscillation formalism: General Approach.

In the three-flavor framework, the flavor eigenstates $|\nu_\alpha\rangle$ ($\alpha = e, \mu, \tau$) are related to the mass eigenstates $|\nu_k\rangle$ ($k = 1, 2, 3$) by the PMNS mixing matrix U :

$$|\nu_\alpha\rangle = \sum_{k=1}^3 U_{\alpha k}^* |\nu_k\rangle, \quad (1.18)$$

$$|\nu_k\rangle = \sum_{\beta=1}^3 U_{\beta k} |\nu_\beta\rangle. \quad (1.19)$$

Each mass eigenstate evolves according to

$$|\nu_k(t)\rangle = e^{-iE_k t} |\nu_k(0)\rangle, \quad (1.20)$$

where E_k is the energy associated with the mass eigenstate ν_k .

Therefore, the time evolution of a flavor state is given by

$$|\nu_\alpha(t)\rangle = \sum_{k=1}^3 U_{\alpha k}^* e^{-iE_k t} |\nu_k\rangle. \quad (1.21)$$

The amplitude for a neutrino initially produced in the flavor state ν_α to be detected as ν_β after time t (or distance $L \approx t$) is:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta}(t) &= \langle \nu_\beta | \nu_\alpha(t) \rangle \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^3 U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} e^{-iE_k t}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.22)$$

The corresponding transition probability is

$$P_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta} = |A_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta}|^2 = \sum_{k,j} U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^* e^{-i(E_k - E_j)t}. \quad (1.23)$$

Here E_k and E_j denote the energies of the mass eigenstates ν_k and ν_j , respectively.

For ultra-relativistic neutrinos ($m_i^2 \ll E^2$),

$$E_i = \sqrt{p_i^2 + m_i^2} \simeq p + \frac{m_i^2}{2E}, \quad (1.24)$$

so that

$$E_k - E_j \simeq \frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2}{2E}, \quad \text{where } \Delta m_{kj}^2 = m_k^2 - m_j^2. \quad (1.25)$$

Substituting this into the probability expression gives

$$P_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta} = \sum_{k,j} U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^* \exp \left[-i \frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E} \right]. \quad (1.26)$$

By expanding and combining terms, we get:

$$P_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta} = \sum_k |U_{\alpha k}|^2 |U_{\beta k}|^2 + 2 \sum_{k>j} \text{Re} \left[U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^* e^{-i \frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E}} \right]. \quad (1.27)$$

After simplification using Euler's formula,

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta} &= \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{k>j} \text{Re}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{4E} \right) \\ &\quad + 2 \sum_{k>j} \text{Im}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin \left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (1.28)$$

The complete three-flavor neutrino oscillation probability in vacuum can thus be compactly written as:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\alpha\beta} &= \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{k>j} \text{Re}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{4E} \right) \\ &\quad + 2 \sum_{k>j} \text{Im}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin \left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E} \right) \end{aligned}$$

The first term represents the flavor conserving component, the second term accounts the flavor oscillations due to the real parts of the mixing elements, and the third term—proportional to the imaginary components of U —encodes the **CP violation** in neutrino oscillations.

1.5 CP Violation in Neutrino Oscillations

In the three-flavor neutrino framework, flavor states $|\nu_\alpha\rangle$ ($\alpha = e, \mu, \tau$) are superpositions of mass eigenstates $|\nu_i\rangle$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$) via the Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata (PMNS) matrix U :

$$|\nu_\alpha\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^3 U_{\alpha i}^* |\nu_i\rangle. \quad (1.29)$$

Neutrino oscillations occur because the mass eigenstates propagate with different phases, giving rise to time- (or distance-) dependent flavor conversion probabilities.

The probability that a neutrino of flavor α converts to flavor β after traveling a distance L in vacuum is:

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{k>j} \Re(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{4E}\right) + 2 \sum_{k>j} \Im(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E}\right), \quad (1.30)$$

where $\Delta m_{kj}^2 = m_k^2 - m_j^2$.

Under CP conjugation, all mixing matrix elements are complex-conjugated:

$$U_{\alpha i} \longrightarrow U_{\alpha i}^*.$$

The oscillation probability for antineutrinos becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{\bar{\alpha}\bar{\beta}} &= \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{k>j} \Re(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{4E}\right) \\
&\quad - 2 \sum_{k>j} \Im(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E}\right). \quad (1.31)
\end{aligned}$$

The key observation is that:

$$\text{Re}(X) \xrightarrow{\text{CP}} \text{Re}(X), \quad \text{Im}(X) \xrightarrow{\text{CP}} -\text{Im}(X).$$

Hence, only the **imaginary term** in Eq. (1.31) changes sign under CP, making it the origin of CP violation.

The difference between neutrino and antineutrino probabilities is:

$$\Delta P_{\alpha\beta}^{CP} \equiv P_{\alpha\beta} - P_{\bar{\alpha}\bar{\beta}} = 4 \sum_{k>j} \text{Im}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E}\right). \quad (1.32)$$

This term vanishes if all matrix elements are real (i.e., if the CP-violating phase $\delta = 0$ or π).

In the PDG parameterization, the PMNS matrix is written as:

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{23}c_{13} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $s_{ij} = \sin \theta_{ij}$ and $c_{ij} = \cos \theta_{ij}$.

The phase δ enters complex exponentials $e^{\pm i\delta}$, affecting both real and imaginary parts of the oscillation amplitude. However, under CP conjugation ($\delta \rightarrow -\delta$), only the imaginary part flips sign.

Let's try to understand it with an example: $\theta_{12} = 33.44^\circ$, $\theta_{13} = 8.57^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = 49.2^\circ$, and we compare for $\delta = +\pi/2$ vs $\delta = -\pi/2$.

Let us define:

$$X = U_{e3}^* U_{\mu 3} U_{e2} U_{\mu 2}^*.$$

Evaluating numerically (rounded):

$$X(\delta = +\pi/2) \approx -0.00378 + 0.03314 i, \quad X(\delta = -\pi/2) \approx -0.00378 - 0.03314 i.$$

Thus,

$$\text{Re}(X) \text{ is unchanged,} \quad \text{Im}(X) \text{ flips sign.}$$

This clearly illustrates that CP conjugation changes the sign of the imaginary component, which leads to the difference in oscillation probabilities between neutrinos and antineutrinos.

- The CP phase δ is present in both real and imaginary parts of the oscillation amplitude.
- However, the **observable CP violation** (i.e., $P_{\alpha\beta} \neq P_{\bar{\alpha}\bar{\beta}}$) depends only on the imaginary part because CP conjugation effectively performs complex conjugation on U .
- This gives rise to the CP-odd term proportional to $\sin(\Delta m_{kj}^2 L/2E)$ in Eq. (1.32).

The CP-violating effects in neutrino oscillations arise due to the complex phase δ in the PMNS matrix. Although δ enters both the real and imaginary parts of the probability amplitude, only the imaginary component is CP-odd and thus measurable through differences between neutrino and antineutrino oscillations.

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{k>j} \text{Re}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{4E}\right) + 2 \sum_{k>j} \text{Im}(U_{\alpha k}^* U_{\beta k} U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin\left(\frac{\Delta m_{kj}^2 L}{2E}\right)$$

The second term is CP-even, while the last term is CP-odd and represents the measurable **CP violation** in the neutrino sector.

Chapter 2

Entanglement and Quantum Correlations in Neutrino Oscillations

2.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, we derived the formalism for two- and three-flavor neutrino oscillations in vacuum and introduced the PMNS matrix including CP violation. We now extend the discussion to a quantum-information perspective, focusing on how **entanglement** and **quantum coherence** emerge during neutrino flavor oscillations. We use the two-flavor neutrino oscillation framework in vacuum and matter developed in [8], [9], [10] and Ref. [7].

Each neutrino flavor component behaves as a quantum subsystem. The oscillation process can thus be regarded as a dynamic redistribution of quantum correlations between the three flavor modes $(\nu_e, \nu_\mu, \nu_\tau)$.

2.2 Quantum Entanglement in Neutrino Mixing (Two Flavor)

The two-neutrino state space \mathcal{H}_ν can be seen as a two-qubit Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$, spanned by the basis

$$\{ |1\rangle_1 \otimes |0\rangle_2, |0\rangle_1 \otimes |1\rangle_2 \},$$

by means of the unitary equivalence defined in the mass basis as

$$|\nu_1\rangle = |1\rangle_1 \otimes |0\rangle_2, \quad |\nu_2\rangle = |0\rangle_1 \otimes |1\rangle_2.$$

In this two-qubit representation, a bipartition of the quantum state space is naturally defined, with respect to which entanglement can be considered. Correspondingly, a neutrino state that is entangled when viewed as a two-qubit state is said to exhibit *mode entanglement*. In two-flavor ($\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta$) mixing,

$$|\nu_e(t)\rangle = \tilde{U}_{ee}(t) |10\rangle + \tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t) |01\rangle,$$

where $|10\rangle$ and $|01\rangle$ are two-qubit flavor mode states,

$$|\nu_e\rangle = |1\rangle_e \otimes |0\rangle_\mu \equiv |10\rangle, \quad |\nu_\mu\rangle = |0\rangle_e \otimes |1\rangle_\mu \equiv |01\rangle.$$

The density matrix for

$$|\nu_e(t)\rangle = \tilde{U}_{ee}(t) |10\rangle_e + \tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t) |01\rangle_\mu$$

is

$$\rho^e(t) = |\nu_e(t)\rangle\langle\nu_e(t)| = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & |\tilde{U}_{ee}(t)|^2 & \tilde{U}_{ee}(t)\tilde{U}_{e\mu}^*(t) & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)\tilde{U}_{ee}^*(t) & |\tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)|^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Similarly, for

$$|\nu_\mu(t)\rangle = \tilde{U}_{\mu e}(t) |10\rangle_e + \tilde{U}_{\mu\mu}(t) |01\rangle_\mu,$$

the density matrix is

$$\rho^\mu(t) = |\nu_\mu(t)\rangle\langle\nu_\mu(t)| = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & |\tilde{U}_{\mu e}(t)|^2 & \tilde{U}_{\mu e}(t)\tilde{U}_{\mu\mu}^*(t) & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{U}_{\mu\mu}(t)\tilde{U}_{\mu e}^*(t) & |\tilde{U}_{\mu\mu}(t)|^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now, as we are familiar with the formalism of Density Matrix and the basics about the entanglement (or mode entanglement). We need to understand how to get the idea for determining the degree of entanglement and to know when Neutrinos are in mixed state and pure state.

So, when the Neutrinos travel since time ($t=0$), the neutrinos in superposition state, are in pure state!

Now the question arises - how mixedness even arise? One of the most important properties of mixedness: $\rho^2 \neq \rho$, when we neglect the other flavor and we only consider one flavor the coherence term in the reduced density matrix is missing. Hence, the that consideration is represents a mixed state but important point to note is that the entire system is still a pure state!!

It is known that **von Neumann entropy** serves as a fundamental tool for quantifying entanglement between subsystems in bipartite quantum systems. The von Neumann entropy, denoted by $S(\rho)$, provides a precise measure of entanglement by characterizing the degree of correlation between subsystems. The density matrix is a mathematical representation that describes the quantum state of a system by incorporating the probabilities of different possible states. The reduced density matrix is obtained by tracing out (integrating over) the degrees of freedom of one of the subsystems from the full density matrix of the entire system. The von Neumann entropy is defined as

$$S(\rho) = -\text{Tr}(\rho \ln \rho). \quad (2.1)$$

When neutrinos are produced at the source ($t = 0$), they are created in a definite flavor state. As they propagate, flavor mixing leads to a coherent superposition of flavor states. Importantly, despite being in a superposition, the neutrino state remains a pure quantum state under unitary time evolution.

For two-flavor oscillations, the neutrino state at time t can be written in

the flavor-mode (two-qubit) representation as

$$|\nu(t)\rangle = \tilde{U}_{ee}(t) |10\rangle + \tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t) |01\rangle, \quad (2.2)$$

where $|10\rangle \equiv |1\rangle_e \otimes |0\rangle_\mu$ and $|01\rangle \equiv |0\rangle_e \otimes |1\rangle_\mu$, and the normalization condition

$$|\tilde{U}_{ee}(t)|^2 + |\tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)|^2 = 1 \quad (2.3)$$

is satisfied.

The density matrix of the full neutrino system is given by

$$\rho(t) = |\nu(t)\rangle\langle\nu(t)|. \quad (2.4)$$

Since $\rho^2(t) = \rho(t)$ and $\text{Tr}[\rho^2(t)] = 1$, the total neutrino system remains in a pure state throughout its evolution.

To investigate the properties of a single flavor mode, we construct the reduced density matrix by tracing over the μ -flavor mode:

$$\rho_e(t) = \text{Tr}_\mu[\rho(t)]. \quad (2.5)$$

Expanding the full density matrix explicitly,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(t) = & |\tilde{U}_{ee}(t)|^2 |10\rangle\langle 10| + \tilde{U}_{ee}(t)\tilde{U}_{e\mu}^*(t) |10\rangle\langle 01| \\ & + \tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)\tilde{U}_{ee}^*(t) |01\rangle\langle 10| + |\tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)|^2 |01\rangle\langle 01|. \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Using the definition of the partial trace,

$$\text{Tr}_\mu(|i\rangle_e |j\rangle_\mu \langle k|_e \langle l|_\mu) = \langle l|j\rangle_\mu |i\rangle_e \langle k|_e, \quad (2.7)$$

the off-diagonal (coherence) terms vanish due to the orthogonality of the flavor modes, while the diagonal terms survive. As a result, the reduced density matrix takes the form

$$\rho_e(t) = \begin{pmatrix} |\tilde{U}_{ee}(t)|^2 & 0 \\ 0 & |\tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)|^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.8)$$

Identifying the survival and transition probabilities as

$$P_{ee}(t) = |\tilde{U}_{ee}(t)|^2, \quad P_{e\mu}(t) = |\tilde{U}_{e\mu}(t)|^2, \quad (2.9)$$

we see that

$$\rho_e(t) = \begin{pmatrix} P_{ee}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & P_{e\mu}(t) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.10)$$

Since $\rho_e^2(t) \neq \rho_e(t)$ and $\text{Tr}[\rho_e^2(t)] < 1$ for $0 < P_{e\mu}(t) < 1$, the reduced state is a mixed state. This mixedness does not arise from decoherence or loss of unitarity, but rather from the entanglement between the flavor modes. While the coherence is absent in the reduced description, it remains encoded in the correlations of the full neutrino state.

2.3 Graphical Analysis using the von Neumann Entropy:

Figure 2.1: Variation of the survival probability P_{ee} , transition probability $P_{e\mu}$, and the von Neumann entropy S as functions of L/E in vacuum. The entropy vanishes when the neutrino is in a definite flavor state and reaches its maximum at points of maximal flavor mixing.

We can see that for the maximally mixed states ,i.e when the existence of both the flavors of the neutrinos are equally probable, the entanglement

entropy is the maximum. It can be observed from the plot that the the entropy is directly proportional to the mixedness of the neutrino modes, the von Neumann Entropy drops the moment the mixedness reduces.

2.4 Graphical Analysis for the Matter Case:

Here, we use the modified formula for probability which arises due to the charged and the neutral current interactions. The effective Potential terms adds up in the Hamiltonian expression.

Now, we use the same expression for the entropy study the variation in matter effects, theoretically as well as experimentally, there will be an effective change in the Oscillation Probability because of the phase shift due to the charged current interaction.

So, by keeping this in mind, I will try to study if the von Neumann Entropy could prove this!

Figure 2.2: Variation of the survival probability P_{ee} , transition probability $P_{e\mu}$, and the von Neumann entropy S as functions of L/E in matter.

As compared the the previous case, the peaks of the von Neumann Entropy changes or varies more than that of the vacuum case, this gives a glimpse of the theory I added initially.

To understand this concept and to draw out more conclusions I will try to

compare these two plots directly!

Figure 2.3: Variation of the survival probability P_{ee} , transition probability $P_{e\mu}$, and the von Neumann entropy S as functions of L/E in matter.

if the entropy for the initial range of L/E is taken into account, where the entanglement entropy for the matter and vacuum case overlaps as for the small range of L/E , the effects of matter will not play a vital role. However, as soon as the interval increases, for the interval (10000 km/GeV – 30000 km/GeV), the probability of oscillation in matter exceeds that in vacuum. This enhancement is primarily due to the effects of matter, particularly the charged-current interactions experienced by electron neutrinos as they propagate through matter. In matter, ν_e experiences an additional potential due to coherent forward scattering of electrons, a phenomenon that does not affect ν_μ . This results in an effective modification of the mixing angle and the mass-squared difference, leading to an increased oscillation probability in this intermediate L/E range. In contrast, neutral-current interactions, which affect all active neutrino flavors equally, do not contribute to flavor conversion, and hence do not alter the oscillation probabilities in the two-flavor approximation. At larger L/E , the matter potential becomes relatively less significant compared to the vacuum term. This leads to a reduction in the difference between the matter and vacuum

oscillation probabilities.

Chapter 3

Computational Approach to Neutrino Oscillation Probability (in Vacuum and Matter)

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we present a computational study of neutrino oscillations using the three-flavor formalism. The phenomenon of neutrino oscillation arises due to the mixing between flavor eigenstates and mass eigenstates of neutrinos, described by the PMNS (Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata) matrix.

The oscillation probabilities depend on the mixing angles, mass-squared differences, the CP-violating phase δ , and the ratio of the baseline distance L to the neutrino energy E (L/E). In this computational analysis, we numerically evaluate the oscillation probabilities for different CP-violating phases using Python.

3.2 Methodology and Computational Implementation

The numerical simulation was implemented in Python using the NumPy and Matplotlib libraries. The code calculates:

- The oscillation probabilities for $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ and $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\tau$ transitions,

- The survival probability of $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$,
- The entanglement entropy among flavor states.

The CP-violating phase δ was varied as 0° , 45° , 90° , 135° , and 180° . The Python script used for these computations is provided below.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Mixing angles in radians
t12 = np.deg2rad(33.41)
t13 = np.deg2rad(8.54)
t23 = np.deg2rad(49.1)

# Mass-squared differences (eV2)
delta12 = 7.37e-5
delta13 = 2.56e-3
delta23 = delta13 - delta12

# Baseline and L/E
L = 1300 # km
LbyE = np.linspace(0.01, 35000, 1001)

# CP phases (in degrees)
CP_degrees = [0, 45, 90, 135, 180]
CP_phases = np.deg2rad(CP_degrees)

for CP in CP_phases:
    def U_matrix(CP, t12, t13, t23):
        s12, s23, s13 = np.sin(t12), np.sin(t23), np.sin(t13)
        c12, c23, c13 = np.cos(t12), np.cos(t23), np.cos(t13)
        U = np.array([
            [c12*c13, s12*c13, s13*np.exp(-1j*CP)],
            [-s12*c23 - c12*s23*s13*np.exp(1j*CP),
             c12*c23 - s12*s23*s13*np.exp(1j*CP), s23*c13],
            [s12*s23 - c12*c23*s13*np.exp(1j*CP),
             -c12*s23 - s12*c23*s13*np.exp(1j*CP), c23*c13]
        ], dtype=complex)
        return U

    U = U_matrix(CP, t12, t13, t23)
```

```

# Compute real and imaginary components for probability terms
U1_real = (U[0][1].conj()*U[1][1]*U[0][0]*U[1][0].conj()).real
U2_real = (U[0][2].conj()*U[1][2]*U[0][1]*U[1][1].conj()).real
U3_real = (U[0][2].conj()*U[1][2]*U[0][0]*U[1][0].conj()).real
U1_img = (U[0][1].conj()*U[1][1]*U[0][0]*U[1][0].conj()).imag
U2_img = (U[0][2].conj()*U[1][2]*U[0][1]*U[1][1].conj()).imag
U3_img = (U[0][2].conj()*U[1][2]*U[0][0]*U[1][0].conj()).imag

# Oscillation probability: electron to muon neutrinos
P_eu = (
    -4 * (U1_real * np.sin(1.27 * delta12 * LbyE)**2 +
          U2_real * np.sin(1.27 * delta23 * LbyE)**2 +
          U3_real * np.sin(1.27 * delta13 * LbyE)**2)
    + 2 * (U1_img * np.sin(2.54 * delta12 * LbyE) +
          U2_img * np.sin(2.54 * delta23 * LbyE) +
          U3_img * np.sin(2.54 * delta13 * LbyE))
)

# Survival probability of electron neutrinos
U1_sur = (U[0][0]*U[0][1].conj()*U[0][0].conj()*U[0][1]).real
U2_sur = (U[0][0]*U[0][2].conj()*U[0][0].conj()*U[0][2]).real
U3_sur = (U[0][1]*U[0][2].conj()*U[0][1].conj()*U[0][2]).real
P_ee = 1 - 4 * (
    U1_sur * np.sin(1.27 * delta12 * LbyE)**2 +
    U2_sur * np.sin(1.27 * delta13 * LbyE)**2 +
    U3_sur * np.sin(1.27 * delta23 * LbyE)**2
)

# Oscillation probability: electron to tau neutrinos
U1_real_tau = (U[0][1].conj()*U[2][1]*U[0][0]*U[2][0].conj()).real
U2_real_tau = (U[0][2].conj()*U[2][2]*U[0][1]*U[2][1].conj()).real
U3_real_tau = (U[0][2].conj()*U[2][2]*U[0][0]*U[2][0].conj()).real
U1_img_tau = (U[0][1].conj()*U[2][1]*U[0][0]*U[2][0].conj()).imag
U2_img_tau = (U[0][2].conj()*U[2][2]*U[0][1]*U[2][1].conj()).imag
U3_img_tau = (U[0][2].conj()*U[2][2]*U[0][0]*U[2][0].conj()).imag

P_et = (
    -4 * (U1_real_tau * np.sin(1.27 * delta12 * LbyE)**2 +
          U2_real_tau * np.sin(1.27 * delta23 * LbyE)**2 +
          U3_real_tau * np.sin(1.27 * delta13 * LbyE)**2)
    + 2 * (U1_img_tau * np.sin(2.54 * delta12 * LbyE) +
          U2_img_tau * np.sin(2.54 * delta23 * LbyE) +
          U3_img_tau * np.sin(2.54 * delta13 * LbyE))
)

```

)

```

# Entanglement entropy
S_eu = -(P_ee + P_eu) * np.log2(P_ee + P_eu) - P_et * np.log2(P_et)
S_et = -(P_ee + P_et) * np.log2(P_ee + P_et) - P_eu * np.log2(P_eu)
S_ut = -(P_eu + P_et) * np.log2(P_eu + P_et) - P_ee * np.log2(P_ee)

plt.xlim(0, 35000)
plt.ylim(0, 1.2)
plt.xlabel("L/E (km/eV)")
plt.plot(LbyE, P_ee, label="$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$")
plt.plot(LbyE, P_eu, label="$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\mu$")
plt.plot(LbyE, P_et, label="$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\tau$")
plt.title(f"Three-Flavor Oscillation ( $\delta = \{np.rad2deg(CP)\}^\circ$ ")
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.show()

```

3.3 Results and Discussion

The numerical simulations were carried out for different values of the CP-violating phase $\delta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ,$ and 180° . The corresponding oscillation probabilities are shown below, each illustrating the variation of P_{ee} , $P_{e\mu}$, and $P_{e\tau}$ as functions of the ratio L/E .

Figure 3.1: Oscillation probabilities for $\delta = 0^\circ$.

Figure 3.2: Oscillation probabilities for $\delta = 45^\circ$.

Figure 3.3: Oscillation probabilities for $\delta = 90^\circ$.

Figure 3.4: Oscillation probabilities for $\delta = 135^\circ$.

Figure 3.5: Oscillation probabilities for $\delta = 180^\circ$.

Analysis and Discussion

For $\delta = 0^\circ$, the oscillation pattern exhibits a symmetric sinusoidal nature. The survival probability P_{ee} of electron neutrinos decreases periodically with increasing L/E , reaching minima where the transition probabilities $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$ attain their maxima. This behavior signifies the conversion of ν_e into other flavors, maintaining total probability conservation ($P_{ee} + P_{e\mu} + P_{e\tau} = 1$). The absence of CP violation results in symmetric oscillation amplitudes and phases.

At $\delta = 45^\circ$, a slight phase shift in the oscillation curves is observed compared to the $\delta = 0^\circ$ case. The amplitudes of $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$ show minor variations, indicating the influence of a nonzero CP-violating phase on flavor transition probabilities. The differences between $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$ become more pronounced at certain L/E values, revealing the onset of CP-induced asymmetry.

For $\delta = 90^\circ$, the CP violation effect becomes more significant. The oscillation peaks of $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$ shift further apart, and their amplitudes differ more noticeably. The interference between mass eigenstates is modified, causing the oscillation pattern to deviate from perfect symmetry. This phase corresponds to a strong CP-violating scenario, where neutrino and antineutrino oscillations would exhibit measurable differences.

When $\delta = 135^\circ$, the oscillation behavior begins to resemble that of $\delta = 45^\circ$ but with inverse phase relationships. The maxima and minima of $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$ interchange positions compared to earlier cases, indicating how CP phase reversal influences the direction of phase shifts. The oscillation envelope slightly broadens, demonstrating that both the amplitude and frequency of flavor transitions are sensitive to δ .

For $\delta = 180^\circ$, the oscillation curves regain approximate symmetry similar to the $\delta = 0^\circ$ case, but with inverted phase relations. The survival probability P_{ee} again shows periodic dips corresponding to flavor conversions, and the oscillation amplitudes are slightly shifted. This behavior indicates that the CP phase primarily controls the phase difference and relative magnitude between the transition probabilities.

Overall Discussion

Across all five CP phases, the survival probability P_{ee} consistently exhibits an oscillatory pattern determined by the mass-squared differences and mixing angles. The transition probabilities $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$ vary complementarily, satisfying the unitarity condition:

$$P_{ee} + P_{e\mu} + P_{e\tau} = 1.$$

As δ varies, the oscillation peaks shift, and asymmetry emerges between $P_{e\mu}$ and $P_{e\tau}$, reflecting CP-violating effects.

Furthermore, the computed entropies S_{eu} , S_{et} , and S_{ut} highlight the degree of entanglement among flavor states. Their variation with L/E shows that flavor mixing induces quantum correlations that depend strongly on both the baseline and the CP-violating phase.

Overall, these results confirm that the CP phase δ plays a crucial role in shaping the oscillation

patterns and flavor transition dynamics in the three-flavor neutrino framework.

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